

Exploring issues relating to school placement and services provided to young children with
autism within the Jamaican Context -A Mini Case Study

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Introduction

“Discrimination is the main issue I face with a child diagnosed with autism. I am screamed at, verbally abused and accused of being a poor parent by individuals at church and even strangers... It is distressing and overwhelming at times It is a lonely road for many families in Jamaica who have children with autism... Furthermore, many preschools do not have trained staff to cater to the needs of children with autism...and the cost for private services is extremely expensive.”

Beverly Brown (pseudonym)- Interviewed parent of child with autism.

Maia Chung, founder of the Maia Chung Autistic and Disabilities foundation and a mother of a child with autism was quoted as saying:

"I am tired. I am done..... I am disheartened and I don't see why I should continue..."
(Wilson,2012, par.4)

“...here in Jamaica, the autistic individual is more likely to be treated as a 'mad person', persecuted and ostracized...” (Collinder, 2008.par 5)

"I have got too many calls from parents on the edge - who want to commit suicide because they are frustrated and depressed."(Collinder, 2008.par 6)

These touching expressions echo the shocking yet lived daily experiences of many Jamaican families with children diagnosed with autism. The lack of adequate financial, emotional and psychological support systems, the government’s failure to implement the legislative framework to fully protect the rights of persons with disabilities, woefully inadequate support for the

education of children with autism, as well as the lingering lack of public empathy and support have driven many families to the brink of depression and despair.

This situation is not only reflective of the Jamaican experience but is a worldwide dilemma.

However, within the Jamaican context the lack of political will in addressing the aforementioned issues has led to infringements on the educational rights of the most vulnerable in society: children with disabilities, and in particular autism.

Purpose Statement

The researcher seeks to explore issues relating to school placement and services provided to young children with autism, through the lens of a parent. The researcher will also seek to delve into the multiplicities of complex issues within the Jamaican context with which families with children diagnosed with autism have to grapple. As such, an in-depth interview was conducted with the parent of a six-year-old male child diagnosed with mild autism and speech delay. The researcher will first present the findings from the interview. The findings will then be analyzed with the literature as a source of reference. Finally, the researcher will provide recommendations to address disparities which arise from the analysis of the findings and the literature.

Description of Instrument

In order to gather data for this assignment, a special education needs questionnaire for parents was employed. The questionnaire consists of fifteen questions which required the participant to respond using four options: agree, partially agree, disagree and, don't know. In addition, there is a section adjacent to each question which allows for additional comments, clarifications and explanations. The instrument is also designed to capture data on several other key areas. First, it aims to gather data on the parent's perspective on the support systems provided by the school, for the child's academic, social and emotional development. Second, it purposes to capture data on the level community and governmental support provided to the child and parent. Third, the questionnaire will reveal the parent's level of involvement in two areas: support groups within and outside of the parent's community, as well as participation in training sessions relating to special education organized by community or government agencies. Finally, the instrument is designed to garner more detailed information on the parent's concerns or issues regarding the child's education.

Presentation of Findings

The parent responded to a fifteen section questionnaire. The findings are outlined below:

The parent (Mrs. Brown) stated that she agreed that her child was making good progress at school and was satisfied with the level of support provided by the institution. Prior to being enrolled in this institution, her son attended at privately operated preparatory school. However, he made little progress as the school failed to create a structured programme to cater to his unique needs. She further indicated that she approached the administration of the institution to inquire if the services of a shadow could be accommodated. However, the administration for the school flatly refused her proposal. Mrs. Brown subscribes to the belief that accommodating a shadow in her son's class would have highlighted the deficiencies of that institution. However, since her son was transferred to the new school a year ago he has made significant strides especially in areas as social development and behaviour. Mrs. Brown attributes this to the willingness of the school to accommodate a shadow.

Mrs. Brown further highlighted that public education regarding government programmes and support systems for parents of children with disabilities is woefully lacking. This has led to a 'hit and miss' situation for parents in desperate need of assistance to cater to their children's unique educational needs. She postulated that such a situation within the Jamaican context has negative implications for children with disabilities and has placed them at a disadvantage. Mrs. Brown stressed that she was informed about the 'shadow support system' through a private service she had engaged for speech therapy for her son. She contacted the Ministry of Education and was informed that the service was available. However, she was given two options: either to assume the role of the shadow or locate a suitable one, independent of the Ministry's support. Mrs. Brown chose the latter option. Confused and distressed and without much details on the

criteria for a suitable shadow, Mrs. Brown and her husband went about seeking to locate one. By coincidence, while shopping in a local store she poured out her distress to an employee about the urgent need to find a shadow so that her son could continue his education. The employee informed her that she had an interest in the post and that she had experience in that area of working with children with disabilities. Mrs. Brown then transported the potential shadow to the Ministry of Education where she was informed about the required documents and qualifications. She was subsequently interviewed and employed.

The school then readily accepted the shadow and made adjustment to their planning sessions to accommodate her son's needs. During such sessions, the class teacher and shadow discussed her son's progress as well as how best to meet his needs. The class teacher who is a trained early childhood practitioner plans differentiated activities for the child and communicates these verbally and in writing to the shadow. The shadow is also provided with a private area to facilitate the child's personalized sessions. He is often separated from the class as he makes loud sounds which can distract the other students.

The progress of the child, as well as specific academic, behavioural and social development targets and how they will be attained are regularly communicated either through the shadow or the class teacher to Mrs. Brown. The class teacher and shadow also engage in regular conferencing with her on the topics covered in classes weekly and make suggestions on extended activities at home to reinforce concepts taught. Mrs. Brown finds the staff to be extremely approachable and accommodating to the needs of her son and describes the shadow arrangement as well as inclusive education as the best paths for assisting children with learning challenges.

As a result of the joint effort of the school and parent, the child has improved academically as he is better able to colour and trace. In addition, he has become more sociable. Likewise, he is more

settled in classes with fewer temper tantrums. Furthermore, he also has developed more self-help skills, as he is now able use the bathroom more independently. He can also put on his shoe as well as remove his clothing.

The school also provides the opportunity for the child to be engaged in extracurricular activities and other social events. For example, for sports day, he was placed in a house and was actively involved in training with other students without disabilities for several races. He is also included in the daily devotional exercises which he has learnt to participate in by clapping, while the students and other members of staff sing.

In terms of knowing or establishing a relationship with the Special Needs coordinator at the Ministry of Education, Mrs. Brown indicated she does not know the Special Needs coordinator. However, she mentioned that a Ministry of Education special education specialist regularly checks on the progress of her son and the findings are communicated through the shadow. She however desires to be actively engaged directly in discussions regarding her son's progress with the Ministry of Education personnel and not through a third party.

While Mrs. Brown is satisfied with the support provided by the school, she however laments the grossly inadequate support system for families with children who are autistic as well as the long waiting period for diagnosis through the public system. She noted that when her child was three years old he was sent for testing by a private practitioner to the University of the West Indies hospital, as he was suspected of being autistic. It however took two years for her to receive confirmation of his condition. After confirmation, her son was registered at the Child and Family clinic at the University of the West Indies hospital for clinical support. However, she emphasized that the staff (excluding the doctors) assigned to the clinic are quite insensitive to her son's condition. Furthermore, Mrs. Brown decries the fact that the physical setting and atmosphere of

the clinic lacks sensitivity to children with autism. She highlighted that there is an area in the main waiting room with a large 'silent zone' sign. Members of staff would often use it as a reference point and demand that she controls her child and adhere to the dictates of the sign. This has and continues to ignite many heated disputes between herself and some members of staff.

Mrs. Brown pointed to this example as one of the ironies of the public health system.

In a bid to address her son's speech delay issue, Mrs. Brown registered him at the Children's Hospital for speech therapy. She however discontinued this service as she emphasized that there was no speech therapy provided during the sessions. In fact, there was no interaction with the child. Mrs. Brown explained that the speech therapist simply inquired about the child's physical progress. After discontinuing the service at the Children's hospital, she engaged the services of a private practitioner for speech therapy. However, she discontinued the service because of fiscal constraints. She lamented that the service was at a cost of 56,000 per month for two sessions per week.

Soon after, she registered for the Early Stimulation programme where her son presently receives 45minutes to 1-hour sessions of speech therapy and other clinical support. These sessions are held once every three months. In addition, counselling sessions are also provided for parents to cope with the anxiety and the high emotional stress associated with caring for a child with autism. She is also supported through these sessions which provide practical assistance with developing self-help skills for her son as well as enhancing social and cognitive development. However, Mrs. Brown maintains that the session for therapy is limited and far apart and therefore any strides made are minuscule. To complicate matters there is a long waiting list to receive the kind of intense speech therapy needed as her son suffers from speech delay.

Mrs. Brown also highlighted that special transportation should be provided for children with disabilities. This is so as those with disabilities have to contend with a public transportation system which is hostile and abusive towards them. She pointed to instances when travelling on public transport after therapy with her son when insulting and biting remarks would be hurled at her because of her son's tantrums. She was often labelled as a poor parent who could not control her child.

For Mrs. Brown and her husband, it is a lonely road for parents with autistic children in the Jamaican context. She agonizes over the fact that there are support systems provided for parents as herself, but they are mainly provided in the metropolitan areas as Kingston. Sojourning to Kingston is not only inconvenient but also impossible, in view of her responsibilities as a wife and mother of three children.

In an effort to seek emotional solace, Mrs. Brown turns to her religious organization. However, she is often chided by its members for her child's 'unruly behaviour', which needs to be 'controlled'. As a result, she is often plagued by depression and anxiety.

Exacerbating the situation is the fact that there are no organized support systems or education sessions regarding special education in Mrs. Brown's community. She has however endeavored to create her own support system with another parent in her community whose child is autistic. They communicate regularly and share researched information on how to successfully navigate through the challenges and uncertainties associated with rearing children with autism.

Analysis of findings

Legislative Framework

The Right to Education is basic human Right. (*Universal Declaration of Human Rights-Article 26 – proclaimed in 1948*)

The right to education is a basic human right. As such, on December 10, 1948 the United Nations' General Assembly recognized the right to education as a basic human right (United Nations, n.d). Subsequently, a number of international conventions including the International Covenant of Economic, Social and Cultural Rights has recognized the right to free, compulsory primary education for all (United Nations Human Rights, 2019). The UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (article 24) reiterates that there are five things which a government must do to protect the educational rights of children with disabilities. First, individuals with disabilities must not be denied an education because of their disabilities. Second, individuals with disabilities must have equal opportunity for free quality education. Third, the needs of such individuals must be reasonably accommodated by educational institutions. Fourth, individuals with a disability must receive support to advance themselves educationally within mainstream education. Fifth, the government must ensure that educational environments help such individuals reach their maximum academic and social development, in line with the aim of full inclusion (United Nations, n.d).

In 2014, Jamaica passed the Disabilities Act. Such a legislative framework guarantees the protection of the rights of its citizens who suffer from a disability and is in keeping with the

United Nation’s Convention of the rights of PWDs, to which Jamaica is a signatory. However, to date, it is yet to be implemented as no regulations are in place (Miller,2018). Senator Floyd Morris in the parliamentary debate on the Appropriations Bill in 2018 passionately argued that the failure to implement the Disabilities Act is a mere “mockery of the parliamentary process” (Miller, 2018 par.1). He further postulated that when he ‘looked’ at the budget allocated for the Jamaica Council for persons with Disabilities there were no increases for the fiscal year 2018-2019. This has serious implications for persons with disabilities, including children with autism. As such, many in the public domain have raised questions about the government’s commitment to providing support for and protecting the most vulnerable in society. Foremost among the support which such persons deserve relates to education.

Mrs. Brown spoke to the challenges of locating suitable educational options and support to meet the needs of her son. First, there is a dearth of public education on support systems provided by the Ministry of Education. Hence, it was through a private system that she learned about the ‘shadow support’ programme. This questions the Ministry of Education’s dedication to meeting the needs of young children with learning difficulties. In addition, when Mrs. Brown contacted the Ministry of Education, she was informed that she could assume the role of shadow for her child. However, when one considers the complex nature of competently addressing the educational needs of a child with autism, one questions how it is possible for such a daunting task to be left solely in the hands of a parent who lacks educational expertise in special education. In addition, the fact that she was instructed to source a suitable shadow independent of the Ministry of Education support, runs contrary to Jamaica’s Disability Act of 2014 which guarantees that a child with a disability should not be disadvantaged educationally or kept out of the education system just because of his or her disability (Disabilities Act,2014). During the

period it took to locate, interview and employ the shadow, her son's schooling was temporarily halted for several weeks. Such a situation placed her child at a disadvantage educationally.

Hence, the questions which emerge are: Should the education of a child with a disability be left to coincidence? Could not the Ministry of Education or the educational institution provide active support in locating a suitable shadow?

Furthermore, the Jamaican government's commitment to truly strengthening and building the capacity of educators at the early childhood level to address the needs of children with ASD disorders is an area of contention and is open to question. In 2013 for example, the Ministry of Education through the Education System Transformation Programme (ESTP) hosted a three-day capacity building exercise to train education officers as well as several special education practitioners across the education sector aimed at catering to the needs of children with ASD disorders ("Education Ministry Tackles Autism",2013). The question which emerges however is: Is a three-day capacity workshop adequate to ably support and arm practitioners to meet the needs of all children with autism?

Mrs. Brown passionately maintained that many early childhood institutions lack trained staff in the area of special education and hence many turn parents away because of the lack of expertise in creating tailored programmes for such students. The exclusion of children with disabilities from mainstream education on such a basis is a direct legal violation on several fronts. It is a violation of the 2014 Disabilities Act, the UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities article 24 and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Furthermore, similar to Mrs. Brown's earlier experience, Mann (2013) expounded on the challenge associated with locating learning institution to adequately cater to the needs of children with autism in Jamaica. The result is that many children diagnosed with a disability including

autism are disadvantaged educationally. In a research conducted with several parents, over 50% of respondents expressed concern over the lack of training by staff and the resultant mistreatment of their children. One parent in an interview revealed telling details about her distressing experience where she suggests that corporal punishment was administered to her son as a result of the lack of training to deal with his condition:

“Last year at school he came home with a mark and the teacher said he fell down but there was no scratch or anything like that. There was nothing on the chin or arm to show he had actually fallen so I don’t know. I planned on not sending him back. Period” (p.133).

Slow Pace of Diagnosis and Communication by Governmental Agencies

“I felt my sons’ notes had been lost or they had been forgotten about”

(Bothwell, Braiden, & Duffy, 2010 p. 385)

Another concern for Mrs. Brown was the long duration to receive confirmation of her child’s condition as well as lack of communication regarding resources available through government agencies. A study conducted in the Jamaican context reveals high levels of frustration and the negative impact of the lack of communication regarding resources available for children with autism. Mann (2013) recounts one experience of a parent in this regard who spoke to this situation in the Jamaican context:

“They need a lot of things because there are a lot of children in Jamaica who are autistic but parents do not know where to go, but unlike me, I have been in a situation where I am

familiar with everything, but there are people out there who don't know where to go... So they (government agencies) need to put something in place so when children are diagnosed they can say to the parent right there and then, "Go here. Go there." ... That's why there are many autistic children locked away at home, not because they want to but because they have no other options. If I wasn't fighting hard ya know, my child would be locked away at home too."

The aforementioned situation is a common complaint from parents worldwide. Mann (2013) posits that upon receiving the diagnosis, "many parents recounted that they wished they had received greater information on surrounding resources, treatment, and prognosis for their child" (p.46). Furthermore, Mann (2013) relates the high level of frustration of parent describing the "long waits for evaluation or a lack of information surrounding how to address their concerns for their child's development" (p.46). Regarding the long waits for evaluation, during a research conducted in Ireland one parents commented, "I felt my sons' notes had been lost or they had been forgotten about" (Bothwell, Braiden, & Duffy, 2010 p. 385). This situation needs to be urgently addressed as early diagnosis and intervention as well as communication regarding government support systems and treatments available are crucial to the long term educational, emotional and social development of children with learning disabilities, and in particular autism.

Discrimination and Rejection

“Their place is the school of disabled. What are we going to do with them?”

(Girli,2018. p.5)

Mrs. Brown tearfully expressed her distress after a pre-school where her school was previously enrolled refused to make adjustments to accommodate her child’s leaning needs by accepting a shadow. This kind of discrimination is a shared experience of parents with autistic children in many countries. In Turkey for example, a first world country where the 1982 constitution as well as 2015 Disabilities Act legally guarantees protection from discrimination for individuals with disabilities (Meral &Turnbull,2016), perpetual acts discrimination is rampant against children with autism and their families at the early childhood level. Girli (2018 conducted a study in Turkey with parents of children with autism and recounted their experiences with preschool teachers and staff. In general, the early experiences of the parents revealed encounters with discriminatory attitudes and vociferous efforts to exclude their children from the pre-school education.

Below are a few expressions:

Father 1: “We changed exactly 11 kindergartens. Sometimes we told the diagnosis first and we were rejected from the beginning. Sometimes we did not say it; they noticed the situation and threw us out of the school. We did not give up, tried another one.”

Father 2: “The process to start the kindergarten was very painful. We were dismissed many times. We went to a school for 3 months, another school for 1 month. We were very demoralized, but we did not give up. Finally, we could find a good teacher.”

One teacher in elementary said to one mother: “Their place is the school of disabled. What are we going to do with them?” (p.5)

Hence, despite the legal strides, many parents have to contend with discrimination from educators who unfortunately cling to the ideology that children with disabilities should either be excluded from inclusive educational experiences or that they should not make the necessary adjustments to meet the needs of such children.

Furthermore, acts of discrimination directed at families of children with autism in Turkey has reached crisis proportion. The prevailing attitude towards families and their children has been fueled by the attitudes as well actions of those in authority and those who serve in parliament to protect the rights of all citizens. Many politicians merely use persons with disabilities as a political ticket in political champions but are slow to pursue vigorous implementations to protect their educational rights. The negative attitude towards children with disabilities including autism within the Turkish context is reflected in the Turkey’s first Disability law uses an outdated word for disabled translating to mean “defective”. To date, many within the Turkish context adopt this view of children and adults with disabilities including autism. Moreover, despite legislative guarantee of compulsory education for children at the early childhood stage only a small number of these children have access to early childhood education (Gurel, 2018). As a result of the lack of support, rejection and discrimination “many families with children with disabilities are “praying for their kids to die before them” (Sussman, 2011, par.21) and many children with disabilities as autism are “kept sequestered at home Hidden in the back yard” (Sussman,2011, par. 2-3).

Fundamental Right of Parental Involvement in the Education Process

Legal mandates in countries as the United States and worldwide require parental participation in the planning, monitoring and implementing of school-based intervention for children with special needs (Lee, 2019; Right to Education 2018,). Despite such legal dictates the literature consistently points to the failure to recognize the importance of parental inclusion in the education of children with disabilities as one of the major challenges with “multidisciplinary educational teams” (Bonner, Esquivel & Ryan, 2008. p.234). Bodies of literature further maintain that high-quality, reciprocal parent–teacher communication which is essential and expected, is seldom achieved, especially between parents and teachers of children with special needs, such as ASD (Azad, Kim, Marcus, Sheridan, & Mandell, 2016). Furthermore, interactions between parents and academic staff is usually limited, with shared information and mutual understanding frequently lacking. Exasperating the situation is the fact that expectations and goals are often inconsistent or poorly communicated (Ackerman-Spain, Murray, Ryley & Williams, 2011; Billingsley & Lake ,2000). Subsequently, many families report that they are dissatisfied with interactions with the academic staff at the institution in which their children are enrolled. (Billingsley &Lake, 2000).

The example of the Browns’ family to a great extent defies the literature in this regard. During the interview with Mrs. Brown, she repeatedly reiterated that she was satisfied with the bond forged between herself and the institution to which her son belongs. This relationship is underpinned by mutual respect and recognition of the right for parental participation in the planning, monitoring and implementing of school-based interventions as well as the child’s legal right to inclusive education. She is likewise satisfied with the extent to which the school was willing to make needed adjustments in its internal organization to accommodate the shadow and

in creating a tailored programme for her son. Mrs. Brown repeatedly pointed to regular conferencing to discuss the child's progress, his developmental targets and how they would be attained. The school maintains an open door policy which facilitates Mrs. Brown's active involvement in her son's academic, social and emotional development. She is allowed to visit the school at will and the principal and staff accommodate her concerns about her son's overall development.

However, Mrs. Brown pointed to an area of unease. A special education specialist from the Ministry of Education visits the school regularly to monitor the programme for her son. After the visit, the findings, concerns and recommendations are communicated to the class teacher, then to shadow and finally to Mrs., Brown. She has however voiced her displeasure with how information of this nature is disseminated to her through a third party. She contends that she should be actively engaged in dialogue with the Ministry of Education personnel on the development of her son as well as suggestions for modifications to his educational programme. This right is protected legally and should be recognized.

Financial Dilemmas

“The lack of viable solutions and interventions from the government has plunged many families into financial ruin” (Wilson,2012. Par 7).

Another area of disquiet for Mrs. Brown is the cost for her son's education. While the shadow is paid by the Ministry of Education, Mr. and Mrs. Brown must independently finance all incidentals associated with his schooling such as books, materials and tuition. Mrs. Brown also bemoans the high cost for private medical treatment as speech therapy. In addition, government

funded facilities as Stimulation Plus is woefully lacking as her son is seen once every three months. Complicating matters is the long waiting list for the intensive speech therapy which her son desperately needs.

The experience of Mrs. Brown mirrors the lived experience of many Jamaican families affected by autism. Collider (2008) cites Maia Chung, founder of the Autism and Disabilities foundation in Jamaica bemoaning the non-existence of support systems for children with autism as well as the “super costs” (par.13) associated with as speech therapy in the private system. Wilson (2012) quotes Maia Chung as “pointing to a lack of viable solutions and interventions from the government” (par.7) which has plunged many families into financial ruin. She cited a meagre subvention given in 2009 Of \$100,000 Jamaican dollars to assist some children. However, when one cogitates on the fact that the cost for one child for speech therapy averages over \$50,000 per month along with other miscellaneous, such an offer is an insult to children with disabilities and reinforces the scant regard for such the most vulnerable in society.

Many families, as a result of financial strain have been forced to turn to non- profit organizations as the Maia Chung foundation. Her foundation has raised over 10 million to provide families with financial support for books, school materials and even groceries. Despite her efforts however many families can barely manage on a daily basis. Maia Chung disclosed that many have voiced the desire to “commit suicide because they are frustrated and depressed” (Collinder, 2008,par.6).

According to Mann (2013), after spending her life savings to cater to the needs of her child with autism, one distraught parent in Jamaica exclaimed: “My money has run out. My money has run out because these services are not cheap, so my money has certainly run out. I can’t afford ABA anymore. I can’t afford OT anymore. I can’t afford anything here anymore” (p.122). Another

mother interviewed during the study conducted by Mann (2013) in articulating the non-existence of financial aid from the government stated: "...So even if you're trying, ya say, alright I don't have the money and you're rocking back on da government, but there's no rock to rock..." (p.122).

In more recent times however, the government has made attempts at providing support for children with autism and their families. The extent to which these are effective and support the educational needs of children with disabilities is open to question. For example, in 2018, the Jamaican government through the Ministry of Labour and Social Security expanded the Early Stimulation centre (stim –plus). This centre caters to children from birth to six years old. Among the services provided is the assessment and creation of early targeted intervention programmes for children with disabilities as autism. The centre likewise offers counselling services for parents as well as training in catering to the individual needs of their children (Angus,2018).

The challenge with programmes as Stim-plus though, is how limited they are in catering to the holistic needs of autistic children. Mrs. Brown highlighted that her son is seen only once every three months and she agonized over the long waiting list for speech therapy. Hence, while the government has made strides in its efforts to support families with autistic children, the results have been miniscule. Mann (2013) speaks of the experience of one parent with the Early Stimulation centre. He highlighted the fact that the resources (human or otherwise) are stretched thin or overburdened as a result of the high influx of children with disabilities whose parents who cannot afford the high cost associated with private treatments. The result is that many children with disabilities as autism cannot adequately access the services provided. One parent recounts that her son was only able to receive one short stint of treatment:

“...we have 10,000 people with autism. And no place to assist them for them to get help with speech therapy. Cause dem said in 2007 I went to get Peter da one term and dat’s it. She said you need to come back and, up to dis point, I went over dere and dey’re supposed to call me and den don’t call me” (p.124)

Furthermore, as children with autism get older there are not much government funded agencies to cater to their needs; leaving families to take on the burden of caring for exponential costs associated with their educational and clinical needs.

What obtains in the Jamaican context however, stands in sharp contrast to the realities of first world countries as the United States. There are various agencies and programmes designed to provide financial support to families affected by autism in that region. These include state and federal disability benefits, supplemental security income (SSI), social security disability insurance (SSDI), Medicaid ,community and state financial assistance and family grant opportunities. These provide assistance with transportation, respite care, medical treatment, in-house support, among others. Also, many state legislatures have enacted autism-specific insurance mandates that require for-profit, commercial, health maintenance organization (HMO), and nonprofit health insurance companies regulated by the state to pay for medically necessary and evidence-based autism treatments (Autism Speaks, 2019; Kelly,2015). Furthermore, since the ratification of the Autism Insurance Act of 2008, all private insurers must provide for diagnosis, treatments, psychological services, consultations, behavioral therapies, care services, and medication for individuals with ASDs up to 21 years of age. (Special learning Inc., 2019.). This is the ideal for which the Jamaican system must strive.

This however does not mean that the systems implemented in such countries have always been or are utopic. For example, during the early 1900’s autistic children were largely ignored and

neglected and even denied full inclusion in public education until the passing of the Individuals with Disabilities Education Act in 1975 (IDEA) (Hunt & Marshall, 2002). Even after this time in the mid 1990's public schools still used techniques as the scream room, restraint and verbal abuse. Scream rooms were usually rooms with a single coloured wall, contained a chair /desk but no windows. The child was kept in the room for long durations at a time. The resulting feelings of isolation and frustration would result in the child scraping the walls, banging their head or inflicting other forms of self-injury (Raiti, 2014). The IDEA however, has come a far way in creating equity for children with autism. It was revised since 2004 and the law mandates that states provide all children with free and appropriate public education tailored to meet their unique needs in the least restrictive environment to allow for the greatest opportunity for interaction with children who do not have a disability (Autism Speaks, 2019, Raiti, 2014). In addition, early intervention services are provided at no cost. The IDEA likewise provides state with federal grants to institute early intervention programmes as well as support systems in the form of counselling and training for parents at no cost to them (Autism Speaks, 2019)

Emotional and psychological Impact of autism on families.

The emotional stress of caring for a child with ASD rivals that experienced by combat soldiers and Holocaust survivors (Mann ,2013).

In additional to the overwhelming economic impact of caring of children with autism in Jamaican, there is also the emotional and psychological toll with which families must grapple. While financial aid is more readily available in developed countries, emotional trauma is a thread which runs through the fabric of all families of autistic children.

Hooyman & Kramer, 2006, as cited in Hartmann (2012) posits that:

“An autism diagnosis can be perceived as a loss for the family. The grieving process associated with the birth of a child with disabilities is complicated by the parents’ grieving the death of the ‘expected’ baby while at the same time trying to accept the ‘imperfect’ baby. Even though they have the joy of being able to hold and love their baby, their life is suddenly and drastically changed” (p.2).

To further expand this point, researchers have found the emotional stress of caring for a child with ASD rivals that experienced by combat soldiers and Holocaust survivors (Mann ,2013). This is so as parents who care for children with a disability often grapple with stressful experiences. The families, in some cases become overwhelmed to the point that it affects the home and leads the family into serious crisis. Parents with children who are autistic may experience more stress than parents of naturally developing children as a result of ‘loneliness, guilt, family disintegration, lack of friends, emptiness, and social exclusions (Girli, 2018; Hartmann, 2012; Nelson, 2015). Bilgin and Kucuk (2010) and Girli (2018) highlighted decades of research conducted studying the psychological health of parents of children with autism. The results indicated that parents with autistic children were more adversely affected psychologically than parents of developing children or mentally handicapped children without autism. The severity of the psychological impact corresponded to the severity of the autistic symptoms. In a study conducted in Turkey, Bilgin and Kucuk (2010) highlighted six categories of stress factors financial problems, the child’s aggressive behaviour, the lack of spousal support, woefully inadequate educational interventions as well as access to education and acts of discrimination. The literature further posits that within this culture mothers are more impacted psychologically as they are primary caregivers. The overwhelming burden of providing such care has pushed

many mothers to resort to unhealthy ways of coping with the stress as smoking and alcohols abuse. Many even battle suicidal inclinations.

While the situation has not adversely disturbed relationships within the Brown's family, as with many other families affected by autism (Mann,2013), Mrs. Brown attests to the loneliness, feelings of guilt and depression which plagues her daily. Exacerbating her struggles is the lack of organized support groups in her locality through which she can vent her emotions, receive emotional solace and be supported by others who can empathize with her challenges. There are a few support groups, however, but they are located in the urban areas and as such are not accessible to her. Hence, Mrs. Brown must tread the familiar lonely path, with depression as her constant companion. On this path, she is all too often ostracized and labeled as a poor parent who cannot control her child by the general public or members of her religious community.

The Role of Support Groups

“We take strength from each other and solve our problems. I think it provides good emotional and social support for us” (Girli,2018. p6).

The literature on this topic speaks to the critical role of a good support system for parents of children with autism. Girli (2018) contends that the stress families face after the diagnosis “decreased especially through the support they received from people and institutions such as doctors, educators and therapists” (p.2). Support groups do not only help parents cope with the unique aspects of their children's disorder but it will also help them learn how to manage their feelings and emotions when faced with the challenges of raising a child with the condition (Stanford Children's health,2019, Nelson, 2015). Support groups also enable parents to share

information with one another, such as information about therapies or new programmes, anecdotal experiences of living with autism, and advice on how to deal cope with the challenges associated with the disability (Mann,2013). They also allow parents to vent their frustrations, and have their feelings validated and understood. Through these groups, information is disseminated on training workshops, school services as well as support programmes. For many families the most outstanding benefit is the opportunity to forge long-lasting friendships as many are treated as social outcast in their communities (Special Learning Inc,2019).

Conclusion and Recommendations

When the findings were analyzed with the literature as a reference point, several disparities arose which needs to be addressed. Foremost, public education in several key areas must be given priority by the government.

First, there must be an intensive educational public campaign to sensitize the Jamaican populace on the prevalence of autism and other disabilities as well as the need for empathy and respect for such individuals and their families. Developing public awareness should do much to mitigate acts of discrimination and abuse directed at individuals with disabilities as well as their families (Mann,2013). Jamaica is legally bounded by the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities which it has ratified. This legal legislation (article 5), mandates all states to fulfil their duty to eliminate discrimination (United Nations, n.d).

To communicate its recognition of this legal mandate, the Jamaican government through its arm the Ministry of Labour and Social Security must move with alacrity to implement the Disabilities Act passed over four years ago. This crucial piece of legislation must be implemented immediately to eliminate discrimination faced by children with disabilities including autism in the public domain as well as from educational institutions. Article four of the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities directs that states must “protect and promote the human rights of persons with disabilities” (p.5). One basic human right is the right to education. The implementation of the necessary regulations to accompany Jamaica’s Disabilities Act will ensure that educational institutions and in particular early childhood schools honour their legal obligation to retrofit or modify their institutions to accommodate children with disabilities. This will ensure that children with disabilities are not temporarily or permanently excluded from the educational system.

Another kind of public education is crucial. This is concentrated public education through the media on government support systems provided for individuals with special needs; as much of this information seems to be shrouded in secrecy. This will mitigate the confusion and stress experienced by parent of autistic children as they seek suitable options to meet the educational needs of their children. Such an intensive government initiative will communicate to society that protecting the more vulnerable in society (children with disabilities and particularly autism) is a priority and will ensure that they are not disadvantaged during their educational journey.

Second, the long duration to receive confirmation of a child's condition as it relates to a disability, as well as a lack of communication regarding resources available through government agencies need to be addressed with the utmost urgency. This issue is a sore point for many parents worldwide. However, if children with disabilities are to receive the appropriate support to develop academically, emotionally and socially, it is imperative that parents receive confirmation of the diagnosis sooner than later. It is likewise vital that government agencies provide greater information regarding surrounding resources, treatment options, and long term prognosis of conditions.

Third, the Ministry of Education must expend effort and financial resources to invest in teacher training for inclusive education, if it is to bring genuine meaning to its Mantra: 'every child can learn and every child must learn'. Orientation and preparation of teachers for inclusive education should begin with the commencement of teacher training at teachers' colleges and Universities. During this period, teachers in training should not only be introduced and trained to deliver child-centered pedagogy which caters to the array of issues relating to the various types of disabilities, but should be sensitized to the legal framework which will regulate their practice. This will address negative attitudes towards children with disabilities and ably prepare teachers

in training to create a supportive inclusive environment (“Floyd Morris Tear those barriers down”,2018; Unicef, 2012). Also in -service educators at early childhood institutions should be trained through workshops and supported by Ministry of Education personnel who should monitor programmes implemented for children with disabilities to ensure that the needs of such children are accommodated. During such workshops, educators should be reminded of and or sensitized to the legal framework in which they operate and which obligates them to provide the best quality education within their resources.

Furthermore, another area of concern is the level of training by staff who interface with children with autism as well as their families at government funded facilities. During the interview, Mrs. Brown related that she is often ostracized by members of staff (excluding the doctors) at the Child and Family clinic. She is often chided for lacking parental skills. In many instances the doctors intervene and apologize for the behaviour of the staff. They often times rue about the lack trained staff for the unit. The UN’s Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities speaks directly to this issue. Article four calls for governments “to promote the training of professionals and staff working with persons with disabilities” (p.5). Certainly, such training would necessitate being sensitized to the nature and range of the conditions from which children with autism suffer. Such training will do much to lesson acts of discrimination directed at such children as well as their families.

Fourth, public facilities which cater to the needs of children with disabilities and in particular autism must be retrofitted or modified to reflect sensitivity to their conditions. It is quite ironic that Mrs. Brown was greeted by a ‘silent zone’ sign at the Child and Family clinic as certain behaviours (as making loud sounds) are common to children with autism who suffer from speech delay. This has resulted in many embarrassing situations for her and has been the source of

perpetual heated exchanges between herself and members of staff who demand strict adherence the area being a silent zone. This is reflective of the scant disregard for children with autism and their families, as well as ignorance of autism as a condition. The physical setting and atmosphere of such facilities should be an oasis from the cold outdoors and should promote the emotional wellbeing of parents and children with special needs.

Fifth, the Jamaican government should negotiate with insurance companies and then enact the necessary legislations so that children with disabilities are not deprived of essential medical treatments as speech therapy. In addition there needs to be increased budgetary allocations to the Jamaica Council for Persons with Disabilities and other government agencies which provide essential services for children with autism, so as to ease the financial burden on their families.

Finally, support groups or agencies, whether government or non-government sponsored need to be more accessible to families who reside outside of the metropolitan areas. This is so, as those who reside in the rural areas crave to benefit from such support systems as many feel like social outcasts in their communities and many are at the brink of a psychiatric meltdown. During such interactions many can benefit from the interchange of encouragement, emotional solace provided; and the dissemination of essential information about their children's disabilities, coping strategies; as well as information about agencies (government or non-government) which can provide additional support (Girli, 2018; Mann, 2013; Special Learning Inc, 2019; Stanford Children's health, 2019).

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